

BB-2208

HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Individual Assignment 2

Title:

Case analysis of S & R Aquafarm using the standard causal model of HRM.

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Submission date:

11th November 2020

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ABSTRACT

Founded in 2011, S&R Aquafarm is a small company running the aquaponics business. Among the advantages of this business system is a system that combines conventional aquaculture with the preservation of aquatic animals such as fish in aquariums with hydroponics, and planting plants in water in a symbiotic environment. The company has achieved a lot. However, some key issues cause them to find appropriate solutions, especially in human resource management. Based on the standard causal model, the problem can be reduced by managing the company's human resources. Appropriate HR strategies and practices have been included to give a positive impact on its outcome, and it can directly improve the company's performance, both internally and financially. Achieving this means that the business overall strategy has been met. It is very important for the company to have good Human Resource Management so that the company gets quality human resources.

INTRODUCTION

S & R Aquafarm is a small operation business that uses modern farming methods known as Aquaponics. It was founded in 2011 by two founders, father and his son. But currently, it is managed and operated by his son only, Syazwan. Both had no educational background in agriculture, particularly in Hydroponics and Aquaponics, and they also had no previous farming experience. Formerly known as S & R Aquaquest, but because of the modern aquaculture system they used at that time, which is the Recirculating Aquaculture System (RAS), was too expensive and unsustainable in the long run, they had to change their business to aquaponics, which exists to this day. Aquaponics is a combination of both aquaculture and hydroponics in closed-loop systems.

However, due to lack of knowledge, Aquaponics is a challenging learning curve for him, as this is outside his field of knowledge. Syazwan learned and analyse by himself the produces used by local markets and attend courses to understand it. Despite many challenges arise, Syazwan has proven that people who have no experience in this field and have no background in agriculture, can also achieve success and ability to survive in the industry for more than 3 years. The purpose of this research is to identify the key issues that arise in S & R Aquafarm and to provide the best solutions using the Standard Causal Models of HRM (Musa, Pg Hj Idris, and Basir, 2020).

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The problems in the S & R Aquafarm arise because they did not have the knowledge and background in the agricultural and aquaculture systems to be used in the business. This poses a challenge for them to understand and learn the scientific process of these two systems and to understand how the two can interact with each other and co-exist in these Aquaponic systems. Secondly, it is a challenge to progress in acquiring new experience or skills for Aquaponics, because there is a lot to learn and this is beyond his field of knowledge.

However, despite these challenges, their progress in the field of aquaponics shows that people with little or no knowledge at all and educational background in agriculture can still run the aquaponic system, but provided they should be given proper guidance or training. Apart from that, the problem arises because of the challenge they are facing now which is the scale of S & R Aquafarm operations. The production of their crops is in limited quantities, as they operate only in their residential area. This makes them have to be selective about what they can produce and more

focused on specific crops only. Nevertheless, there are also advantages when focusing on niche markets, as the owner has the advantage of charging premium prices to customers for the crops produced, but niche markets have limited demand for these produces, and usually demanded low quantities. This led to another challenge to find a suitable niche crop to be planted in an aquaponic system that has the right market value and has a lot of demand for the crops produced. When there is no demand for the crops, this will cause losses to them as the crop will be discarded.

Pest infestation and fungus problem are also one of the issues that arise in S & R Aquafarm, as Aquaponics is considered organic when compared to other landless farming methods. This system only relies on fish to provide nutrients for the crops. Addition of chemicals into the system can affect the fish as well as the bacterial cycle which can also offset the natural cycle of the system. This causes them to be more selective in choosing the products since most of the agricultural products sold in the market are made up of chemicals that can endanger the fish. Other alternative solutions, such as using Neem Oil are more expensive than conventional prevention. (Musa, Pg Hj Idris, and Basir, 2020).

CASE ANALYSIS

S & R Aquafarm can be said successful because it has achieved awards such as sustainable business awards and the most innovative enterprise awards. Moreover, one of their huge achievement was part of 21 international business finalists and shortlisted by Shell Global for the *LiveWIRE* Top 10 Innovators Awards. However, some problems arise making it limited and unmanageable due to improper human resource management.

New businesses are often run by sole proprietors or partnerships, where the owner is the employee of their company. Nevertheless, most successful companies tend to hire employees' overtime to take on basic work duties and the company's management responsibilities. The company will create a human resources department responsible for managing their employees and their well-being once they grow (Hamel, n.d).

Human Resources (HR) department is crucial to the success of every organization. Without an effective and efficient HR team, there will be no talented and dedicated people in the company. The things that HR does are often forgotten because most of them are behind the scenes. After all,

HR plays an important role in developing a company's strategy by enhancing employee perceptions across the workforce and providing a holistic experience for employees, and overall, it can benefit and assist the company to meet their long-term goals (Talent adore, 2017).

Figure 1; Standard Causal Model of HRM

The Standard Causal Model of HRM shown in Figure 1 is used to analyze the key issues arising in S & R Aquafarm. Figure 1 shows how HR activities aligned with organizational strategies that lead to improved overall business performance, according to the model. The aim is to show HR effectiveness when its strategy is in line with the business strategy. HR strategy will be generated from the overall strategy. After that, it follows with HR practices such as training and performance appraisal, that lead to an outcome from employees, like employee's commitment, motivation and satisfaction. Thus, this brings benefits directly to the organization as it can improve the internal and financial performance of the organization.

In the standard causal model, there are two relationships. First is the unmediated HRM effect and the second one is reversed causality. In the unmediated HRM effect, HR practices can directly improve internal performance, without affecting HR outcomes. For example, good employee training can directly lead to better performance. Meanwhile, reversed causality shows that a stronger financial performance, such as increases in sales or better margin, can lead to more

investments and better outcome in HR practices and HR outcomes respectively. Therefore, strong performance leads to a better outcome. (Vulpen, n.d)

Figure 2; the standard causal model for S & R Aquafarm

Based on the case analyzed, key issues that arise in S & R Aquafarm, can be improved and solved by following this model. If they have proper HR, the company can achieve better outcomes by using all the strategies and practices, leading to better performance. First and foremost, S & R Aquafarm needs to have an overall strategy to achieve their overall goal or long-term goal, which is customer retention and competitive advantage. Then follow by HR strategy where it plays an important role as a connection between employees and the organizations, given the competitive nature of the workplace today, as well as the existence of external competitors.

Figure 2 shows the standard causal model for S & R Aquafarm. Due to the lack of knowledge and educational background in the field of agriculture, this makes the owner lack skills in doing the works, and inexperienced. He should improve his knowledge by taking more courses to further develop his skills and acquire more knowledge to meet the company’s goals. With the unmediated HRM effect, learning and development practice will directly improve internal performance, such as, with the high knowledge and skills, it helps them to produce better product quality and customer satisfaction.

For the next problem, the owners only run the business within their residential area, and this causes them to produce crops in small quantities only. Therefore, he needs to find a suitable place to

produce his crops so that the products will not be affected. HR must practice a safe, healthy and comfortable workplace, which makes employees comfortable and satisfied while working, thus, this will make them stay loyal with the company for a long time. Furthermore, when employees feel safe and satisfied with their workplace, this will motivate them to work harder and will produce more high-quality crops. These outcomes will result in better internal performance, which is, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. Customer satisfaction leads to a positive impact on financial performance. It means that when customers are satisfied, they will spend more on the products, so this can increase their sales and profits. By using the reversed causality, if they have high profits it can lead to more investment in HR practice and better HR outcome.

Next, the problem they face is finding the right niche crops to meet the right market value and demand. HR should have practiced by creating programs, such as teamwork programs to improve the quality of their products and to prevent the crop from being discarded. Based on the program, leader and employees will work together on some tasks and make decisions the way they want to deliver good results. This will encourage employees to work together and improve in decision making. Therefore, this method will lead to a positive impact on the internal and financial performance of the organization, in terms of earning high profits and the number of products demanded will be higher than before.

Aside from that, S & R Aquafarm has an issue regarding pest infestation and fungus, and the suitable prevention for that is by using Neem Oil. However, the price is too expensive. To solve this problem is by recruitment and selection. The company need to recruit and select candidates who specialize in preventing the problem. Thus, this will lead to a competitive advantage in the workplace. This will be enabled them to be more productive and will result in more sales or higher margins compared to its market competitors.

ALTERNATIVE SOLUTIONS

Alternative solutions can be considered to improve the company's HR and build a successful business. When running a business without an educational background and working alone to grow a business, everything will be difficult and limited. One of the alternative solutions to assist in the development of S & R Aquafarm is to hire people who expert in agriculture, especially specialize in aquaponics systems. So, they can share a lot of knowledge and can reduce the owner from failure. However, it also has its disadvantages, because by hiring expertise, the owner may not have the same continuity in the relationship with the employee and the owner also has to spend high fees to pay the expert (AllBusiness, n.d).

Apart from that, perhaps additional insights and suggestions, if a broader training perspective is taken, to further develop employee learning in terms of sharpening their skills and competencies. Training involves individual processes that involve in acquiring proficiency in certain skills or competencies (Bishop, 2003 as cited in Cardon and Stevens, 2004). The benefits can increase their productivity and work commitment, as well as the opportunity to learn in keeping up with industry changes. The disadvantage, however, is that there is not enough time to train employees due to busy schedules, and more likely they will move to other organizations that offer better benefits and salaries once they have been trained and updated with all the latest knowledge and skills.

Next possible solution is to use a systematic approach with knowledge sharing. Knowledge sharing is an approach that helps to exchange and share innovative knowledge, such as information, skills and ideas between individuals in the workplace. The advantage is that the success of knowledge sharing can generate shared intellectual capital, including employee expertise and organizational ability to innovate. The disadvantage, however, is to find such innovative knowledge, which also requires a more detailed plan for the future.

Next, the possible solution to the problems they face such as the limited scale of S & R Aquafarm operations and the problem of pest and fungus is by seeking investors. Investors can help contribute money to the business. The money can be used to purchase suitable equipment, purchase suitable workspace or stores, and also it assists in developing products. However, unlike regular loans, the disadvantage is, when investors buy ownership of the company, they have equity in the business.

It means that the investor will be entitled to a portion of the money generated from the sale, once the company is sold (DeFelice, 2016).

RECOMMENDATIONS

As a recommendation, from the alternative suggestions given above, it is best to hire people who have expert knowledge in the appropriate field. This is because, besides it helps to improve the performance of employees, it also gives many benefits to the company. Although the price of hiring them may be more expensive than regular employees, the outcome of their work can help in improving the product quality. Better product quality will directly attract many customers because of their satisfaction with the product. Therefore, the more satisfied customers are, the higher the profits that the company will earn. Where ultimately, back to the overall business strategy, which is customer retention and competitive advantage.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, S & R Aquafarm is a successful company that has proven that people who lack knowledge and background in particular education can still successfully run their own business. However, some key issues arise making their business quite limited to manage. Therefore, based on the standard causal model of HRM, to some extent, it can help them in solving their problems. Apart from assisting human resources, it also helps to improve the performance of the company as a whole, both internally and financially, and can directly meet the overall business strategy. Some alternative suggestions have also been included to solve the problem they are facing.

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